

Digital Shinto Communities

also known as "Online Shinto Communities"

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Entry tags: Shintō, Kami worship, Asian American Religions, Technology, Religious Group, Japanese Religions, Shrine Shintō

Digital Shinto communities (DSCs) are transnational networks of Shinto shrines, priests, and lay practitioners supported by various forms of digital technology, in particular social media platforms. These communities center on the ritual veneration of immanent Shinto deities known as kami (神), as "Shintō" (神道) is often translated as "the Way of the Kami." The category of kami is quite broad, including: divine personalities such as Amaterasu Omikami, sun goddess and imperial ancestress, or Inari Okami, particularly revered for agriculture, business, and prosperity broadly conceived; impersonal natural forces or features such as wind, thunder, trees, rivers, and mountains; and human figures. Generally speaking, during Shinto ritual veneration, extensions of a kami's spirit may be called to reside in certain natural and man-made materials (such as a sacred evergreen branch, a mirror, sword, paper or wooden talisman, etc.) to receive offerings and prayers. The emergence of digital Shinto communities can be traced back to the advent of Web 2.0 with the creation of the Shinto Mailing List (ShintoML) on Yahoo! Groups in 2000. ShintoML was extremely active for a decade and enjoyed a membership of over one thousand people, though activity began to taper off in 2010 as ShintoML members migrated to Facebook following the platform's upgrading of group features. Today, as many as ten thousand people are members of an active Facebook DSC, though community engagement spans multiple social media platforms including blogs, Reddit, Discord, YouTube, and Patreon. Some DSCs are public general Shinto interest groups, while others are private organizations for shrine supporters (sūkeisha 崇敬者) and confraternity (kō 講) members. While DSC membership includes Japanese emigrants and their descendants (nikkeijin 日系人), the majority of members tend to be non-Japanese with general knowledge of Japanese history and culture gleaned from popular Japanese media, the internet, and brief trips to Japan. However, the most active members have extensive knowledge of Shinto gained through personal study, several years of membership in DSCs, and ritual practice. A 2019 survey of fifty DSC members and kamidana 神棚 (domestic altar) ownership indicates that the majority live in the United States and the UK, although membership truly spans the globe. Most were raised in nominally Christian households, though others grew up in atheist and Buddhist families. Official group leadership, on the other hand, is populated by a mix of Japanese, Nikkei, and Caucasian administrators ("admins") or moderators ("mods") with varying levels of institutional involvement, ranging from lay shrine caretaker to senior priest. DSC members share most beliefs and practices in common, though they may support different shrines and venerate different kami, the divinities at the center of Shinto ritual. Often without direct access to traditional Shinto spaces and materials such as shrines or sacred talismans (ofuda お札) required for ritual practice in one's home, compounded by a distinct lack of foundational Shinto texts (particularly translated into English) to which they may refer, transnational Shinto practitioners must make creative use of the sources available to them to establish shared knowledge, aesthetics, belief, and practice and properly manage their veneration of kami. These strategies include creating in-group informational resources relating to core Shinto beliefs, texts, and practices such as guidelines and FAQs ("frequently asked questions"), reviewing academic and popular publications on Shinto, sharing photographs of ritual materials and links to trusted vendors, and participating in in-person rituals and ritual livestreams. Though often overlooked, digital Shinto communities hold significant relevance for the study of Japanese religion, online or digital religion, and globalization. Issues of authority and authenticity are raised as DSC members seek, construct, and contest the legitimization of personal approaches to Shinto within a polyvocal network of shrines from various traditions within Shinto, academic and popular literature, online forums, blogs, and

popular media. Moreover, Shinto ontologies of the sacred are reconfigured as DSC members theorize and manage their relationships with kami, their local environment, and everyday experiences.

Date Range: 2001 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Global Digital Shinto Communities Network

Region tags: East Asia, Oceania, Global, North America

Digital Shinto communities span the globe, creating a transnational, online network of practitioners. Early survey data suggests that the majority of Shinto practitioners outside of East Asian are located in Hawai'i and North America.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kaitlyn Ugoretz, "World-Wide Shinto: The Globalization of 'Japanese' Religion," Bloomsbury Handbook of Japanese Religions (New York: Bloomsbury, 2021).
- Source 2: Aike Rots, Shinto, Nature and Ideology in Contemporary Japan: Making Sacred Forests (New York: Bloomsbury, 2017).
- Source 3: Ugo Dessì, The Global Repositioning of Japanese Religions: An integrated Approach (London: Routledge, 2017).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: www.digitalshinto.com
- Source 1 Description: Digital Shinto Project research site run by scholar of Japanese religion Kaitlyn Ugoretz
- Source 2 URL: www.greenshinto.com
- Source 2 Description: "Green Shinto" blog by scholar of Japanese religion John Dougill

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Members of digital Shinto communities live all over the world, so they will encounter different religions depending on where they are located. Early research suggests that transnational Shinto practitioners are certainly in cultural contact with Buddhism, Hinduism, Christianity, Santeria, and several types of Paganism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: While there is some competition between Shinto shrines and Buddhist temples, the relationship is primarily complementary and non-exclusive. For example, many Shinto practitioners also identify as Buddhists, Shugendo practitioners (i.e. Shugenja), Pagans, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: In DSCs, as well as generally in Japan, individuals are free to identify or not identify specifically and explicitly as Shinto practitioners, as well as with any number of other affiliations/identities (e.g. Buddhist, Pagan)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: While Shinto shrines may promote their services and events (for example, on social media) and invite people to attend and participate to support themselves, "conversion" is unnecessary and there is no set agenda for proselytism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: While certain Shinto organizations in Japan such as the Association of Shinto Shrines (Jinja Honchō 神社本庁) have political extensions (i.e. Shintō Seiji Renmei 神道政治連盟) or adjacent pro-Shinto lobbyists (e.g. Nippon Kaigi 日本会議), today Shintō is legally classified as a religion and thus technically separated from the Japanese government. Politicians' Shinto ritual practice are typically considered private acts. The Japanese emperor's position is complicated as both head of state and Shinto ritual leader. As far as the author is aware, there is no significant official political support for transnational Shinto communities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region)

population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Contemporary Shinto does not have any official sacred texts and is often explicitly described as having “no founder, no doctrine, and no sacred texts.” However, there are a number of canonical texts that are recommended within the community, such as the mytho-historical records the Kojiki 古事記 (712 CE) and Nihon Shoki 日本書紀 (720 CE) and prayers called norito 祝詞 recorded in the Engishiki 延喜式 (927 CE).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The primary form of monumental Shinto architecture is the Shinto shrine (jinja 神社).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Tombs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Shinto religious buildings are conventionally called "shrines" (jinja 神社) to distinguish them from Buddhist "temples" (o-tera 佛寺). There are different styles of shrine architecture depending on the lineage. For example, there are marked differences between Ise-style and Inari-style shrines.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: There are several styles of kamidana 神棚 ("kami shelf") structures that form the Shinto domestic altar, ranging from different styles of architecture in the housing (omiya お宮) to the number of ofuda お札 (paper talisman that functions as the focus of kami veneration) accommodated (usually between 1 and 5 "doors," with each door or compartment holding one ofuda for each kami or shrine).

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: For the most part, Shinto devotional markers are held in common among various shrine traditions. These markers include torii gates at the entrance to the shrine and shimenawa ropes, marking one's entry into sacred space; purification basins or fountains with running water (temizya/chouzuya) and ladles used for ritual ablutions when entering sacred shrine precincts; votive tablet (ema) boards, where visitors hang tablets inscribed with a personal wish/prayer or a message of gratitude; and statues of guardian animals, usually "komainu" lion-dogs or another animal associated with the enshrined kami (e.g. Hie shrines with monkey statues). Within the shrine's main worship hall (haiden/honden), you will often find a sacred mirror or another object (generally referred to as a "go-shintai") in which the kami may dwell. Particular shrine traditions may have additional distinct characteristics. For example, shrines dedicated to Inari Okami often exhibit different devotional markers, including messenger fox statues (often sporting red votive bibs) and vermilion torii gates (as opposed to gates of other colors). Unlike most Shinto shrines today, Buddhist iconography like the wish-fulfilling jewel, snakes, and swastikas and architectural elements are often visible at Inari shrines, due to Inari

Okami's continuing association with the Buddhist and Hindu goddesses, Dakiniten and Benzaiten.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Kami may be represented as animals or associated with animal servants/messengers (kenzoku 眷属/眷族) such as snakes, foxes, deer, and legendary creatures like dragons.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Some geographic features are specifically related to or embody kami in Shinto. For example, many mountains such as Mt. Fuji are considered the constitute kami.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Kami may be represented anthropomorphically.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Humans:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of Shinto sacred sites are Shinto shrines, which may themselves be located on or around sacred spaces such as mountains, forests, rocks, and waterfalls. In all of these sacred sites, the presence of kami is particularly felt.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: There is a rich variety of pilgrimage traditions in Shinto, as well as Buddhism. Members of digital Shinto communities may also make pilgrimages to particular shrines in Japan or in their home country and participate in traditional pilgrimages, such as the Kumano Kodō.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: There are a range of theories in Shinto concerning the human spirit/soul (tama 魂/霊, mitama 御霊/御魂), its relationship to the body, and what happens after death. Generally speaking, there is no Cartesian mind/body dualism (see theories on the concept of kokoro 心 or "mind/heart"). The tama

dwells in a person's body and survives after death. Over time, the personal characteristics may fade as an individual tama coalesces with ancestral spirits (sorei 祖霊) or divine spirits (kami 神/神霊).

Reference: Kokugakuin University. "Encyclopedia of Shinto". Kokugakuin University, n.d.. <https://d-museum.kokugakuin.ac.jp/eos/>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: While Shinto has historically posited several realms in which the spirits of the deceased may reside, the majority of beliefs and practices relating to the afterlife are drawn from Buddhism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: According to mythology recorded in the Kojiki (712 CE), one potential realm where spirits of the deceased reside is the dark underworld of Yomi 黄泉 or Ne-no-kuni 根の国, ruled by the goddess Izanami-no-mikoto 伊邪那美命.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: There are several theories in folk religion and Shinto thought, and thus little consensus, dealing with horizontal spaces or "other worlds" where human spirits may reside after death. Historically, mountains have been one such type of space. One specific place mentioned in imperial and regional records of mythology such as the "Kojiki," "Nihon shoki," "Hitachi no kuni fudoki," and "Izumo no kuni fudoki" is the distant land of Tokoyo, often described as being located far across or beneath the sea. Another such horizontal space is Yūkai 幽界, the invisible spirit realm (as opposed to Kenkai 顕界, the visible realm of the living), as popularized by nativist (kokugaku 国学) scholar and Shinto theologian Hirata Atsutane (1776-1843).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Global Shinto Network

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Contemporary Shinto has its own funerary rituals distinct from Buddhism, but Buddhist funerals are still most common. Any Shinto funerary rites are held in the grieving family's home or at the burial site, not at the shrine (due to pollution from death). As of writing, there is no source of data on how transnational Shinto practitioners in particular typically treat the recently deceased. This is left up to the individual family's wishes and local customs.

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: In Japanese Buddhism, the deceased's body is traditionally cremated. Cremation takes place after the wake and funeral ceremony, during which time the deceased is given a new

Buddhist name, a Buddhist priest chants sutra, and family members and friends offer incense and pay their respects. Once the body is cremated, family members will usually participate in "kotsuage (骨揚ぐ)," collectively picking the bones from the ashes with large chopsticks and placing them in an urn. The ashes may be split between multiple urns and then interred in various locations, often including a family, company, or personal grave.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Ashes are typically interred following Buddhist cremation.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Ashes are typically interred following Buddhist cremation.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Shinto funerary rituals

Notes: There are a number of rituals conducted in the home by a Shinto priest, including the pillow adjustment ceremony (makura-naoshi 枕直し) and wake ceremony (tsūyasai 通夜祭). During the pillow adjustment ceremony, the deceased's body is dressed in traditional clothing and positioned with the head laid on a pillow facing north. Offerings of rice, salt, water, and sake are presented to the kami on a temporary altar. During the wake ceremony, mourners gather to express their condolences to the family and give formal monetary offerings in special envelopes. The Shinto priest will report the return of the deceased's spirit to the kami. The room is darkened and the spirit (mitama) of the deceased is solemnly transferred from the body to rest within a spirit vessel (reiji) on a temporary funeral altar, while the casket is transferred for burial or cremation according to the family's wishes. The room is then ritually purified to remove the pollution of death, including the removal of the funeral altar and the preparation of a new altar to house the deceased's spirit until it is joined with the family's ancestors. After the body has been interred or cremated, the family members return home, purify themselves of the pollution of death, and announce to the deceased's spirit that the funeral rites have been completed. The family also thanks the people who have kindly participated in the funeral services. The Shinto mourning period lasts for 50 days. Ceremonial offerings and sacred branches (tamagushi) are presented regularly within the home out of love and respect for the deceased's spirit. The deceased's spirit may then leave the temporary altar and join the host of the family's ancestral spirits in the permanent ancestral spirit altar (tamaya). A number of ceremonies for memorializing ancestral spirits follow on significant anniversaries.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Again, burials are typically handled by Buddhist institutions and according to Buddhist traditions.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: These cemeteries are outside of the purview of Shinto shrines. They may be Buddhist or non-religious.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: This greatly depends on the individual's relationship with a particular shrine tradition and their ideas concerning what kami are. For example, some practitioners consider the sun goddess and Japanese imperial ancestress Amaterasu Omikami to be most powerful and important. Others might consider the primordial heavenly kami Ame-no-Minakanushi or Takamimusubi to be supreme. However, the majority of transnational Shinto practitioners do not make a distinction between kami in terms of supremacy, even if they venerate particular kami.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits are present in the form of ancestral spirits (sorei), who remain in this world and may dwell in a number of places as guardians of their descendants, and they may coalesce or converge with the spirits of the kami (shinrei, mitama).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

Notes: While practitioners can offer food offerings to ancestral spirits (mitama 御霊), including rice, water, and sake, as well as favorite foods, these offerings are given out of gratitude and reverence, not in order to satiate hunger.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings present of central importance in Shinto are the immanent spirits/divinities called "kami" 神. The category of kami is quite broad, including: divine personalities such Amaterasu Omikami, sun goddess and imperial ancestress, or Inari Okami, particularly revered for agriculture, business, and prosperity broadly conceived; impersonal natural forces or features such as wind, thunder, trees, rivers, and mountains; and human figures. Generally speaking, during Shinto ritual veneration, extensions of a kami's spirit may be called to reside in certain natural and man-made materials (such as a sacred evergreen branch, a mirror, sword, paper or wooden talisman, etc.) to receive offerings and prayers. Previously human spirits (ancestral spirits and significant historical figures) may also become kami.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

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↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: While Shinto practitioners offer food offerings (including rice, water, and sake, first fruits, etc.) to kami, divine messengers, etc., these offerings are given out of gratitude and reverence, not in order to satiate hunger. Certain kami or their entourage may have preferences/tastes. For example, it is thought that Inari Okami's fox messengers enjoy offerings of fried tofu.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: However, there are kami who were once human, such as Tenjin (aka Sugawara no Michizane, 845-903 CE). The Japanese imperial lineage also traces its genealogy back to the kami. The divinity of the emperor is not of particular importance to transnational Shinto communities.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Kami, ancestral spirits, and other supernatural beings (e.g. buddhas) may monitor and respond to humans' activities. Generally speaking, supernatural monitoring is common to all kami. There is little evidence to suggest that there are significant distinctions in supernatural monitoring between them. However, particular kami may reward certain kinds of behavior or provide certain kinds of rewards relating to the kami's virtues. Similarly, particular kami may punish certain kinds of behavior or provide certain kinds of punishments. For example, Inari Okami might reward favorable behavior with agricultural or vocational prosperity. Meanwhile, plague kami might punish unfavorable behavior with sickness. It is worth noting that rewards (i.e. genze riyaku 現世利益, "this-worldly benefits") are emphasized and punishments de-emphasized.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: One Shinto taboo is entering sacred space while ritual impure (i.e. not undergoing purification rituals such as ablutions)

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Ritual pollution (kegare and tsumi)

Notes: According to Shinto theology, humans accumulate pollution throughout the course of everyday life. There are two main categories of pollution: "kegare" (汚れ) and "tsumi" (罪). Kegare occurs naturally, polluting a person through proximity to or contact with ritual impurities (e.g. death, sickness, childbirth, and blood). Purification through ritual ablutions are used to cleanse oneself of kegare before entering a sacred space and approaching the kami. Kegare does not provoke moral judgment. Tsumi, on the other hand, is a kind of ritual pollution arising from a person's violation of divine or pro-social taboos, such as incest, agricultural vandalism, violence, and murder, and carries moral weight. Tsumi can also be purified through ritual purification called "harae" (祓). In severe cases, ritual pollution may result in divine punishment from personal misfortune to disease to natural disasters.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: This only applies to Shinto priests at very specific times that require ritual abstinence.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: This is technically a ritual taboo (tsumi).

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: This is technically a ritual taboo (tsumi).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is fundamental in Shinto, particularly for Shinto priests.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is fundamental for Shinto, especially for Shinto priests.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Notes: Practitioners may request boons from the kami, and kami have the power to grant success and prosperity. However, their beneficence is not predicated on ideas about economic fairness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Human's treatment of nature/the environment

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Kami can mete out punishment when angered, but this aspect tends to be de-emphasized in contemporary Shinto.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Kami may punish if one does not observe moral principles for living in harmony with the world.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: For example, kami may cause misfortune or natural disasters in response to irresponsible use of the natural environment.

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: Some kami, simply due to their nature as kami of disease, misfortune, etc., can randomly punish.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

Notes: There is historical precedence for this, but it is not relevant for contemporary practitioners.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

Notes: There is historical precedence for this, but it is not relevant for contemporary practitioners.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Kami are particularly known for their power to bestow rewards or blessings in response to a person's favorable behavior and sincere prayers/requests/offerings. All kami have this ability and may bestow a wide range of blessings. However, particular kami are also known for giving blessings relating to their distinct "virtues" (go-shintoku). For example, the kami Tenjin's virtues include academic success. Okuninushi is known for fostering relationships, particularly romantic/marital relationships, fertility, and safe childbirth. Shinto practitioners will often venerate certain kami when they have particular concerns or are at a given stage in life, in addition to their local kami.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: Scholars of Shinto and Japanese religion more broadly, as well as transnational Shinto communities, have discussed how many Japanese social or cultural norms/conventions are sublimated in Shinto norms and values. These may include values such as respecting vertical and horizontal hierarchy and social distance, which are often embodied/practiced through ritualized behavior such as bowing and using honorific terms of address. While there is some discussion of what Japanese social norms could be elided or adapted to individuals' local customs and norms, there is no concrete consensus on what qualify as "Japanese" norms/values in distinction to "Shinto" norms/values.

Reference: Kawano, Satsuki. *Ritual Practice in Modern Japan*. University of Hawaii Press, 2005. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=WZcBEAAAQBAJ>.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: Historically, Shinto has drawn on the metaphysics of various other traditions, including Buddhism, Confucianism, and Yin-Yang/Onmyodo. However, one distinct and fundamental metaphysical concept in Shinto theology is "musuhi/musubi," a spiritual essence or creative, connective, life-giving force. The pollution (kegare or tsumi) that accumulates on the human heart (kokoro) disturbs or blocks one's proper connection with the generative flow of musubi, which may impact one's vitality and their relationships with both humans and kami. Following pro-social behavior and avoiding or routinely purifying oneself of pollution promotes musubi and consequently has positive effects on one's life and the life of their community.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Notes: Kami can be considered metaphysical entities. There is no explicit distinction as

to whether different kami emphasize or require different virtues/norms.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: However, since Shinto and Buddhism have a long history of combination/syncretism and the two are not mutually exclusive today, Shinto practitioners may also believe in Buddhist concepts like karma.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Kami are nowadays often represented and conceptualized as being anthropomorphic. However, kami were not originally conceptualized in this way until the influence of Buddhism and its anthropomorphic iconography.

Reference: Hardacre, Helen. Shinto. Oxford University Press, 2016.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Shinto.html?hl=&id=_Q81DQAAQBAJ.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Sincerity is emphasized.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - No
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - No
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Harmony with other humans and with nature is often emphasized.
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes

Notes: Not being wasteful is emphasized.

- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– No
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– No

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Physical cleanliness/orderliness may be linked to the concepts of ritual pollution (kegare and tsumi, described above). Particularly, before entering sacred space, a person is expected to perform ritual ablutions of the hands and mouth to cleanse themselves of impurities and prepare to approach/encounter the kami. At formal ceremonies, such as the offering of a sacred branch (tamagushi), neat and formal attire (a kind of orderliness) is also expected.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Monetary offerings are customarily given before personal prayer and to a shrine for ritual services or items rendered. The majority of shrines within Japan accepted offerings of cash. For transnational Shinto practitioners, many cannot physically visit a shrine to pay in cash, as the closest shrine may be several states away (in the case of the United States) or in another country. Some shrines outside of Japan accept donations and membership fees by check, wire transfer, and electronically. The most common method is through PayPal, but shrines have also used newer technologies/platforms such as Patreon.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: They are not exactly required of lay practitioners, but visits to shrines, participation in ceremonies and festivals, and offerings/prayers at one's home altar are encouraged.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Participation in private, household rituals is not required but certainly encouraged in DSCs. These rituals include prayers and offerings and focus on a sacred talisman (ofuda お札), elevated on a stand or housed in a domestic altar (kamidana 神棚).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Participation in large-scale rituals is not required and is often impossible for lay practitioners who are physically distant from Shinto shrines and priests. However, participation in-person or online is encouraged. Shinto priests are required to participate. These large-scale rituals include New Year's visits (hatsumōde 初詣), semiannual Great Purification rituals (Ōharae 大祓), and seasonal festivals (matsuri 祭り) and holidays.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Digital Shinto communities are best understood as a transnational network of Shinto shrines, clergy, and lay practitioners connected by the internet, especially social networking platforms like

Yahoo Groups, Facebook Groups, and Discord. Shinto shrines may be located both within and outside of Japan. The majority of lay practitioners within these networks live outside of Japan in a wide range of nation-states that truly span the globe.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Shinto shrines are part of historical shrine lineages and networks, composed of main or central shrines and branch or auxiliary shrines. The majority of shrines world-wide (some 80,000) are formally part of the Association of Shinto Shrines (Jinja Honcho 神社本庁), though several large shrines are independent, such as Fushimi Inari Taisha and Kotohira-gu. The majority of Shinto shrines outside of Japan are technically affiliated with the Jinja Honcho. Transnational Shinto practitioners involved in digital communities primarily interact with Shinto shrines online a variety of ways. They may be parishioners of a particular shrine or members of a confraternity (ko). Many shrines outside of Japan have websites and Facebook groups. Personal communications, such as requests for ritual services and items or information, often take place over email or chat services like Facebook Messenger. Ritual items may be exchanged in-person or via mail services, sometimes through proxies. Ritual events may be performed for practitioners physically in-person or streamed online, via platforms like Zoom, YouTube, and Instagram.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The state government.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Many shrines have membership associations (e.g. worshippers' association [suukeikai 崇敬会]; confraternity [kou 講]) that have membership fees.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Participation varies by the individual and the country in which they live or have citizenship.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Members of transnational digital Shinto communities communicate online in many languages. The most common language used is English, followed by Japanese. Communication in other languages is facilitated by translation services built into online platforms like Facebook, which typically rely upon Google Translate. Gaining proficiency in Japanese is generally considered important, if not necessary, for long-term engagement with and practice of Shinto ritual. Members may share language learning resources, translations, and transliterations to this end. A survey of fifty practitioners' domestic ritual practice in 2019 concluded that the majority who use traditional Shinto liturgy called *norito* recite them in Japanese, rather than English, even when English is their first language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: There are general and also shrine-specific ritual calendars for festivals, ritual purification, etc.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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